

The Effect Of Organizational Well-Being On Organizational Commitments Within The University By Applying Psychological Climate As The Moderator Variable

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 12, 2020

Accepted:
September 01, 2020

Keywords

Organizational well-being, Organizational commitment, Psychological climate, University.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4010867

Abstract

This research aims to determine the influence of Organizational Well-being on Organizational Commitments, which is moderated by the psychological climate of private universities in Jakarta. The research was based on a quantitative study with convenience sampling data collection techniques. Respondents of this study were 216 lecturers and 216 employees (n= 432) working at five private universities which are accredited A in Jakarta. It also applied data collection using the Well-being scale organization developed by the study of coefficient Alpha of 0.951. Scale Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (Meyer & Allen, 1997) was applied to measure the organizational commitment with coefficient Alpha of 0.786. The psychological climate scale (Ardiwinata, 2013) was also applied to measure the psychological climate with coefficient alpha of 0.920. The data analysis technique on this study applied structural equation modelling (SEM) with Lisrel 8.8 software. The results show that the psychological climate moderates the influence of Organizational Well-being on Organizational Commitments. The influence of Organizational Well-being on Organizational Commitments will be higher if it is supported by an increasing psychological climate. Conversely, if psychological climate support is getting lower, then the commitment to the organization will also decrease. Therefore, the psychological climate acts as a moderator variable as research findings suggest that the psychological climate manages to modify the relationship form between Predictor variables (Organizational Well-being) and Response variables (Organizational Commitment) in which the psychological climate interacts with Predictor variables as well as being the Predictor variables.

1. Introduction

Currently, development demands a change in technology and economics. Therefore, organizations must also evolve over time. In its development, organizations need employees who are capable of working well and contributing to the productivity and well-being of the organization. Economic uncertainty and employment opportunities lead to significant challenges for the emotional well-being and the relationships of individuals who will enter the workforce and organizational life (Di Fabio & Kenny, 2017; Masten, 2014). This aroused organization interest in identifying further the well-being of the organization and resources that can create a healthy organization (Di Fabio & Kenny, 2019).

The well-being of the organization was characterized by the organization ability to promote and care for individuals, or help their members to prosper and develop themselves. A prosperous organization is an organization that can attract and care for its employees so the employees can perform optimal tasks, provide services for the community and create a positive work environment. A positive work environment will create an atmosphere that supports every individual to develop their potential by establishing good relations between superiors and subordinates, co-workers and stakeholders. This positive work environment will motivate individuals to work productively and form positive behaviors within the Organization (Prilleltensky & Prilleltensky, 2006).

Sancassiani, Campagna, Tuligi, Machado, Cantonel, Carta (2015) explains that the well-being of the organization is the first step towards the organizational development process. The organizational well-being has benefits for both organizations and their employees. It results in a prosperous organization which will have an impact on both sides. It is clear then, that individuals and organizations cannot be separated because they have a positive relationship and thus the system within the organization can run optimally.

The Organization Well-being will increase when supported by organizational commitment, namely Affective Commitment. The affective commitment suggests how individuals feel about their organization, which includes feelings of accomplishment while working within the organization. This is the reason organization plays an important role for individuals, especially in providing social support, such as accommodating the employees with coaching supervisors and being open to feedback. These are to motivate employees and encourage them demonstrate optimal work performance.

One reason that supports the establishment of strong organizational commitment in oneself is the psychological climate (Naami & Nezhad, 2009). Organizational well-being that is not supported by a healthy psychological climate will affect the employees, that they will not be committed to the organization and will lead to turnover. On the other hand, healthy psychological climate will support the relationship between organizational well-being and individual's organizational commitment.

The Psychological Climate can be conceptualized as an individual phenomenological experience in an abstract process, in a situation related to the work environment. In this case, individuals would assess and understand their surroundings, because the working environment that supports employees will increase the workers' commitment to the organization, due to the positive support when they are doing their jobs (Wołowska, 2014). The psychological climate in this study was one of the variables of moderators, which would influence and strengthen the relationship between the organizational well-being towards the employees' organizational commitment. The psychological climate also describes the individuals' behavior in a group or organization that is inseparable or segregated. It shows the contextual individual characteristics interactions, how it will strengthen or weaken the organizational well-being influence to the organizational commitment.

Based on the current phenomena taking place in a non-conventional work place, such as in a higher education institution (a university), it requires human resources to execute the operational function. The operational function can run well if the human resources, the lecturers and the staffs, are committed to the organization. Environment also contributes to the work attitude in order to accomplish the vision and mission of the university (Parker *et al.*, 2003). In this research, environment is organizational well-being moderated by the psychological climate. Thus, this research aims to examine the effect of organizational well-being on organizational commitment, in which psychological climate is the moderator in a university. The formulated hypothesis of this research was the influence of organizational well-being towards organizational commitment will be moderated by the psychological climate in a such way that the effect of organizational well-being on organizational commitment will be stronger when positive psychology climate exists.

METHODS

Participants

Participants of the study was recruited voluntarily from five private accredited A universities in Jakarta. A questionnaire was distributed to the participants, who were lecturers, teachers and employees at the university. There were 216 lecturers and 216 employees (N = 432), in which men dominated the participants (N = 236), more than the women (N = 196). The number of participants who didn't have a structural position was 79.16% (N = 342), while those who have the structural position were 20.84% (N = 90).

Measure

The well-being of an organization was measured using the organizational well-being measurement instrument developed by a three-dimensional researcher. They were Effective Environment, Reflective Environment, Affective Environment, and had an item of 64 with four response options from "the very fit" to "the very unsuitable". The reliability of the Cronbach alpha on each of the measuring instrument's dimensions ranged from 0.889 to 0.920.

The psychological climate was measured using a measuring instrument developed by Ardiwinata (2013) consisting of 52 items with four response options from "the very suitable" to "very inappropriate". Cronbach Alpha reliability was as much as 0.945.

The organizational commitment was measured using an Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) developed by Meyer and Allen in 1990, consisting of 18 items covering three dimensions of the Affective Commitment, Commitment Continuity and Normative Commitment. The reliability of Cronbach's alpha on each dimension ranged from 0.631 to 0.761.

RESULTS

Figure 1. Model Conformance Test Results

The figure 1 shows the model's test results indicating the model fits the data. It can be viewed in the following criteria (Adam, 2018):

Table 1. The Fit Model Criteria

Goodness of fit parameter	Criteria	Result	Decision
Chi-Square (X^2) / Degree of Freedom	$2 \leq \text{Chi-Square } (X^2) / \text{df} \leq 3$	$46,95 / 30 = 1,56$	Fit
P-value Chi-Square	$\leq 0,05$	0,025	Fit
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	$\text{RMSEA} \leq 0,08$	0,036	Fit
Goodness-of-Fit-Index (GFI)	$\text{GFI} \geq 0,95$	0,98	Fit
Standardized Root Mean Square Residue (SRMR)	$\text{SRMR} \leq 0,05$	0,017	Fit

The test result for the model suitability shows that each of the Goodness of Fit parameter meets the criteria. As seen in Figure 1, the organizational well-being significantly affects the organizational commitment at the university level ($t \geq 1.96$). Meanwhile, the psychological climate doesn't affect the organizational commitment of lecturers and employees ($t \leq 1.96$). If the psychological climate becomes the moderator at the university level between the organizational well-being and organizational commitment, which made significant results, then the following can be seen as variable contributions to structural equations:

Table 2. Structural Equations

Variable	T-Value $\geq 1,96$	Standardized Loading Factor (SLF) ≤ 1	Details	R^2
Organizational Well-Being	12,83	0,56	Significant	
Psychological Climate	0,85	0,03	Not Significant	0,44
Moderation	5,58	0,22	Significant	

Based on Structural Equation table above, the value of the R^2 , was detected in each of the Relationship Equations. The R^2 value serves to show the extent to which each of the variables freely affects the bound variables. Inconclusive 44% variation of the organizational commitment is possible, due to the influence of the organizational well-being and the moderation of the psychological climate.

As seen in the table above, it explains that the organizational well-being variable with the T value of 12,83 and the 0,56 parameter, shows that the organizational well-being variables are positively influential towards organizational commitments at the university level. The number also means that if the organizational well-being value is increased to 1, then the level of organizational commitment is expected to increase to as much as 0,56. The same also applies in the case of Psychological Climate moderation as the variable, it results in significantly positive organizational well-being. This means that if moderation value is increased to 1, the level of organizational commitment is expected to increase to as much as 0,22.

DISCUSSION

Theoretically, the organizational well-being can influence organizational commitment. Organizations that place individuals according to the skills they possess with a clear task and role, provide facilities and infrastructures that support their performance, effective communication, and supportive working team, make the individuals able to demonstrate organizational commitment in the form of optimal work outcomes (Oades, Steger, Fave, & Passmore, 2017). The results of the research is in accordance with the previous theoretical concept stating that the organizational well-being influences the organizational commitment (Prilleltensky & Prilleltensky, 2006). It can be analyzed from the T value of 12.83, with the R^2 value of 0,44 and the P-value result of 0.02 or smaller than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) which means that Ha1 is received. Thus, it means that the organizational well-being significantly affects the organizational commitment of lecturers and employees at private universities as much as 44% (0,44). The results of this study also were supported by the research conducted by Coli and Rissotto (2015) which found that the organizational well-being ideally reflects the attitude of employees who demonstrate their organizational commitment, such as feeling happy when executing a task.

Researchers also found that the Psychological Climate does not affect the organizational commitment significantly. This is evident from the value of T 0.85 ($t \leq 1.96$). However, the psychological climate is significantly influential when acting as a moderator between the organizational well-being and organizational commitment. It was demonstrated by the T value of 5.58 ($t \geq 1.96$), which means that the psychological climate effects strengthen the well-being factor of the organization with organizational commitment. In other words, Ha2 is received. This is in line with the research described by Nammi and Nezhad (2009), that one factor that makes the individual demonstrate the organizational commitment is the psychological climate.

The positive psychological approach recognizes that a healthy organization must have a psychological climate promoted at interconnected four levels (individual, group, organizational and inter-organizational process) (Henry, 2005). Meanwhile, the interconnectedness of these levels will result in healthy characteristics in individuals and organizations. Healthy characteristics in individuals are emotional intelligence and the ability to relate with others. At the organizational level, the healthy characteristics are the good system, the structure and climate of a healthy organization (Vakola, Tsaousis, & Nikolaou, 2004). Healthy Characteristics in individuals and organizations is proven to have a significant relationship with the organizational well-being (Di Fabio & Kenny, 2019). Eisele and D'Amato (2011) also found that positive psychological climate positively affects individual work attitude, that is organizational commitment.

Good health function in individuals and organizations is based on the presence of qualified relationships between co-workers and social support (Blustein, 2011). Reich and Hershcovis (2011) asserted that good relations with co-workers and social support does not only contribute to academic success, but also healthy social relations in the family, school, community and employment. The quality of relationship with colleagues and community also indicates that an organization has a positive workplace. Characters of a positive workplace are often associated with motivation, physical health, performance, a solid team, effective communication, and organizational commitment. Based on these findings, the researchers concluded that the psychological climate reflected in a positive workplace can promote the organizational well-being to affect individual's organizational commitment.

This research implies that private universities need to create a positive workplace to promote organizational well-being, therefore affecting the quality of human resources, that is the lecturers and employees. Lecturers and employees who feel happy when working within the university will reflect their emotions through their behavior, especially when performing their functions in the teaching and learning process. The forms of this behavior shown by the lecturers and employees when they are prosperous at the university are high dedication, loyalty, commitment and happiness in carrying out their role. All of these can happen because they are allowed to develop themselves. The good example of this concept would be when lecturers are enabled to perform Tridharma values (Three Pillars), while the employees are given the training session to support the university system.

Limitations on the study of data collection is related to non-availability of lecturers and employees of certain faculties and units within the university, and it made it hard to complete the surveys and research

questionnaires covering a certain degree of integrity of the lecturers and employees. Therefore, further studies need to consider the relationship between these variables to participants from various faculties and units within the university to represent all faculties and units. Furthermore, it is necessary to include the social desirability measurement tool when collecting data to know which participants are giving the actual response.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study stated that the organizational well-being is positively significant to the organizational commitment. Furthermore, this study proves that the psychological climate variable moderates the influence of organizational well-being to organizational commitment. The organizational well-being in the university context does not only emphasize the tangible factors, such as salary, profit, and benefits, but also the intangible ones, i.e. individuals can freely develop themselves in order to explore creativity and improve the system in the university context. Universities have to create a climate that supports the performance of lecturers and employees in order to have a positive perception related to the work environment. This climate will improve the well-being of their work. Employees who feel satisfied at work will contribute optimally to the organization. Then, employees will also hope the university appreciate their effort. The balance between hope and reality will make the workers feel satisfied and show a positive relationship with the university in leading the establishment to organizational commitment.

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